

Contingency Leadership Model in a Changing Educational Landscape for an Improved Work Commitment and Performance of Classroom Executives

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to determine the relationship of between contingency leadership model and teachers work commitment and performance. The study utilized descriptive-correlational design which involved the participation of 181 teachers in Tiaong I district. The study utilized survey questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient will be used at 0.05 level of confidence. The data gathered indicated that the perception of the respondents on contingency leadership practices as to situational control as observed in terms of Leadership style and Situational Features and as to Qualities of Followers, situational condition is Highly Observed. In terms of Goal Setting and Expectancy, Directive Clarifying, Achievement-Oriented and Participative is observed while Supportive is highly observed. The perception on Decision making as to Autocratic and Consultative and Collaborative are perceived to be observed. The teacher respondents are highly committed as to Task-Oriented and Motivation and committed as to participation. While the teacher respondents work performance as to Teaching effectiveness, Managing time and Performing duties, the teachers are performing while in terms of Learning Delivery they are highly performing. The findings gathered in the study indicated that there is significant relationship between contingency leadership model and work commitment and performance of classroom executives, thus null hypothesis is not sustained.

KEYWORDS: contingency, leadership, work commitment and performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Education fosters the development of human personality, cognition, and social skills. It also prepares people for life's events. As a result, people are assigned a specific status in their own society and wherever they live. Al-Shuaibi (2014) goes on to say that education is more specifically the activity of acquiring knowledge and information that can help one lead a fulfilling life. However, recent global changes and situations including health crises and improving educational system have resulted creation of new challenges. Therefore, people working in the Educational Institution are under immense pressure to meet the expectation of the society in providing quality education. In order to adapt to these changes and challenges Education leaders must be able to practice effective and efficient leadership styles that promote work commitment and good performance of its subordinates.

In areas where educational institutions emerge and become active, schools are frequently at the top. In reality, schools are an essential part of the larger social framework of society. In terms of method, organization, structure, and functional characteristics, all innovations and changes in society or the larger world, according to Turkkahraman (2015), have a direct influence on education and schools.

Leadership is essential in the diverse and intricate systems found in Philippine schools. In setting up the working environment, providing resources, and influencing employees' innovative work behaviors through management, encouragement, and motivation, school directors are essential, claims Archeo (2022).

According to Machumu (2014), educational institutions play a crucial role in the education of the next generation, and school administrators are held accountable for their institutions. In today's era, leadership style greatly affects teachers' performance in the field of teaching. A teacher who is motivated to perform their duties, committed to work and perform well probably has leaders who provide guidance, support and appreciation to their performance. **Literature Review**

1.1 On Leadership

The working environment, current events, the type of educational platform being used, and the wellbeing of the students are all directly related to how effective a leadership style is (Santos, 2021).

Castillo (2019) noted that effective teachers recognize the potential in others and work to help them realize that potential. Faculty and staff become leaders when they accept responsibility for their decisions, hold themselves accountable for the results of their

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activities, and are personally aware of the consequences of their choices. A great principal will tell you that one of their responsibilities as a leader is to support the growth of their staff members into top achievers.

There is not a single greatest or exceptional leadership approach that functions in every situation; what functions in one setting may not perform at all or perhaps have dysfunctional results in another. These theories suggest that there is no one leadership style that can be employed or applied in all workplace situations and that the best kind of leadership depends on contextual elements. Effective leaders may change their leadership style to fit the demands of the group, the situation, and the objectives to be achieved as a result (Vidal 2017).

1.2 On Work Commitment

According to Luthans, dedication to an organization demonstrates fidelity and care for its success. An organization with devoted employees will see the excellent performance, low resignation rate, and brief absences that are anticipated, as cited by Arifin (2019). The findings show that in an organization, instructors' quality is determined by their level of job satisfaction and dedication. If the administrators encourage, direct, and commend them, beginning teachers have high morals and are prepared to be more devoted. According to Shoaib (2017), it improves their confidence, self-esteem, and morale.

Another study also reveals that visionary management leadership has a beneficial effect on organizational commitment and work satisfaction (Top 2015). The studies revealed a connection between organizational commitment and work satisfaction and organizational management. A principle must be managerially competent in order to implement the management. The management competency may be associated with teachers' dedication to their jobs and sense of job satisfaction.

1.3 On Work Performance

Kennerly's research demonstrates that work happiness is one of the most crucial elements determining instructors' performance because when staff members are happy, their performance increases (Celdran, 2020).

Success in every organization depends on the combined efforts of all its members, including its leaders and employees. To understand organizational success, several scholars and practitioners have carried out extensive investigations to develop the theories of leadership, organizational commitment, and work satisfaction (Aalateeg 2017).

Cerna (2014) asserts that the head of the school has a significant impact on how well students, instructors, and the institution perform. So that the teachers and other staff members under their supervision will cooperate appropriately in achieving the school's vision, it is crucial that school administrators possess strong leadership qualities and use appropriate strategies when exercising their authority, accountability, and empowerment.

2. METHODOLOGY

The researcher used the descriptive correlational method of research design in conducting the study. Rillo (2018) cited descriptive research as a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, processes, trends, and cause-effect relationships and then making adequate and accurate interpretation about such data with or without or sometimes minimal aid of statistical methods.

The respondents of the study were the public elementary school teachers of Tiaong District I. Specifically, it involved the participation of 15 Public Elementary Schools with the total of 181 public elementary teaching personnel of Tiaong I District designated as Teacher I-III and Master Teachers.

The study used survey questionnaires. The first part of the research instrument inquired on the demographic profile of the respondents. Part II is the survey questionnaire composed of 85 items, it was rated by checking the appropriate space for your answer as follows; 5- highly observed, 4- observed, 3- moderately observed, 2- somewhat observed, 1-not observed. It includes; 15 items related to Situational condition, 20 items under goal setting and expectancy, 15 items in decision making, 15 items related to work commitment and 20 items for job performance of public elementary teachers based from their school head's contingent style of leadership. It was used to rate the extent of effectiveness of contingency leadership practices to teachers' work commitment and performance on the given indicators.

To answer specific questions identified and to test the hypothesis as well as to properly analyze the data gathered through the questionnaire, appropriate statistical tools were utilized. Mean, Standard Deviation, frequency and percentage were used to answer the descriptive questions.

To determine the relatedness of Contingency leadership and Work Commitment and Performance of Teachers, the Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient was used at 0.05 level of confidence.

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3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

School	No.of Teaching Personnel	Actual Respondents
Aquino ES	7	5
Ayusan ES	16	11
Behia ES	11	10
Bukal ES	17	12
Bula ES	11	13
Bulakin ES	15	9
CMRMCS	56	44
DCHU ES	20	9
Lalig ES	8	8
San Agustin ES	9	9
San Francisco ES	8	5
San Jose ES	11	7
San Pedro ES	13	10
Tamisian ES	8	6
Tiaong East ES	23	23
Total	233	181

Table 2. Perceived Situational Condition as to Leadership Style

Indicators	Mean	VI	SD
1.consults teachers before making decisions.	4.46	0.56	O
2.provides a system of disseminating information on how the task can be done.	4.43	0.53	O
3.conducts class observations.	4.44	0.59	O
4.outlines school activities and goals properly.	4.46	0.54	O
5.provides technical assistance and instructional pedagogy in teaching.	4.48	0.56	O
Overall	4.45	0.43	O

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed , 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed

The table shows that the teacher respondents perceived that Contingency Leadership practices in situational condition as the leadership style is observed.

Leadership is essential in the diverse and intricate systems found in Philippine schools. In setting up the working environment, providing resources, and influencing employees' innovative work behaviors through management, encouragement, and motivation, school directors are essential, claims Archeo (2022).

In Tiaong district, the 15 schools included in the study are led by principal or school head. Some of the responsibilities of principals and school head according to Republic Act 9155 are as follows: Setting the mission, vision, goals and objectives of the school; Implementing, monitoring and assessing the school curriculum and being accountable for higher learning outcomes; Developing the school education program and school improvement plan; Introducing new and innovative modes of instruction to achieve higher learning outcomes; Encouraging and enhancing staff development.

Table 3. Perceived Situational Condition as to Qualities of Followers

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1.allows teachers to follow instructions but may give opinions and suggestions.	4.51	0.52	HO
2. possesses critical thinking skills.	4.45	0.52	O
3.manages to ease the burden of teachers by being dependable and flexible to look ahead on what needs to be done.	4.39	0.60	O
4. manifests versatility and have intent on high performance.	4.45	0.55	O
5.encourages teachers to accomplish tasks that are given to them.	4.54	0.55	HO
Overall	4.54	0.55	HO

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed , 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed

The table shows that the teacher respondents perceived situational condition as to Qualities of Followers as Highly Observed. Among the indicators, allowing teachers to give suggestions and opinions and encouraging them to accomplish tasks has the highest mean. In Tiaong, teachers were asked for suggestions during faculty meetings, these suggestions were also raised by the principal in district meetings with the supervisor. The district of Tiaong I conducts LAC sessions, school and district INSET. This is in line with DO

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no.35, s. known as the Policy on the Learning Action Cell(LAC), this policy fully supports continuing professional development of its teaching personnel.

Table 4. Perceived Situational Condition as to Situational Features

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. considers teachers' abilities and strength in assigning task.	4.53	0.53	HO
2.makes the decision by majority favor.	4.44	0.59	O
3.considers teachers' and school's needs in making decisions.	4.49	0.55	O
4. makes decisions based on the given situation.	4.51	0.53	HO
5.recognizes individual differences and behavior in handling conflicts.	4.46	0.54	O
Overall	4.49	0.48	O

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed

The table shows that the teacher respondents perceived situational condition as to Situational Features as Observed. However considering teachers abilities and strength in assigning task and making decisions based on the given situation are highly observed. A system to identify the strengths and weaknesses in the delegation of different tasks among teachers to contribute effectiveness because it can ensure if the skills and knowledge of the teachers are appropriately utilized as stated by Laygo (2020). School heads in Tiaong considers their teachers abilities before distributing workloads and coordinatorship for them to maximize the skills teachers have. Meetings were done beforehand to ensure alignment of assigning task to the teachers abilities.

Table 5. Perceived Goal Setting and Expectancy as to Directive-Clarifying

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1.explains what is expected from teachers.	4.48	0.54	O
2.informs teachers about what needs to be done and how it needs to be done.	4.51	0.53	HO
3.provides standard, rules and regulations for the teachers to follow.	4.50	0.56	HO
4.explains what is the expected level of performance of teachers.	4.48	0.57	O
5.explains properly the assigned tasks to teachers .	4.50	0.57	HO
Overall	4.49	0.49	O

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed

The table shows that the teacher respondents perceived Goal Setting and Expectancy as to Directive-Clarifying as Observed. However, among the indicators, informing teachers about what needs to be done and how it needs to be done, providing standard, rules and regulations and explaining assigned tasks to teachers properly are highly observed.

In Tiaong, principals and school heads are the ones who inform teachers about different guidelines issued by the Department. They are responsible in disseminating information, direct teachers and explain tasks assigned to them, how it should be done and the standards to be followed. Principals regularly conduct faculty meetings to inform teachers about the activities and tasks to be done.

Table 6. Perceived Goal Setting and Expectancy as to Achievement-Oriented

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. sets goals for teachers' performance that are quite challenging.	4.43	0.57	O
2. encourages continuous improvement in teachers' performance.	4.52	0.55	HO
3.challenges teachers' ability to meet most objectives.	4.46	0.56	O
4. sets consistently challenging goals for teachers to attain.	4.44	0.55	O
5.expects teachers to perform to the highest level.	4.39	0.58	O
Overall	4.45	0.49	O

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed

The table shows that the teacher respondents perceived Goal Setting and Expectancy as to Achievement-Oriented as Observed. Among the indicators, encouraging continuous improvement in teachers performance is highly observed.

In the District of Tiaong, Supervisor and Principals encourage teachers to pursue Graduate Studies for their professional growth and Development. Continuous improvement of teachers through attending seminars and pursuing graduate studies may be resulted to promotion.

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Another way to encourage teachers to improve performance are the incentives given to them yearly. One of these is the PBB or Performance Based Bonus, it is a top-up incentive given to government employees based on their performance and contributions to the accomplishment of their department's overall targets and commitments.

Table 7. Perceived Goal Setting and Expectancy as to Participative

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. involves teachers in making a decision.	4.54	0.55	Highly Observed
2. considers teachers' ideas, opinions and suggestions.	4.49	0.58	Observed
3. consults teachers before doing a specific task.	4.44	0.58	Observed
4. asks teachers for suggestions on activity schedules.	4.50	0.57	Highly Observed
5. considers suggestions from teachers concerning how to carry out assignments.	4.48	0.55	Observed
Overall	4.49	0.50	Observed

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed

The table shows that the teacher respondents perceived Goal Setting and Expectancy as to Participative as Observed. However, among the indicators, involving teachers in decision making and asking them for suggestions are highly observed.

In Tiaong District, teachers are actively participating, especially in scheduling of activities. Teachers in the district follow specific time and schedule of activities as seen in school calendar. They also participate/cooperate during meetings and orientation conducted for carrying out school activities.

Participative leaders according to Path goal Theory consult with their employees and ask for their input before making decisions. This behavior would be well-received in a workplace where the employees are personally invested in the outcome and results of their work.

Table 8. Perceived Goal Setting and Expectancy as to Supportive

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. maintains friendly working relationship with teachers.	4.54	0.58	HO
2. focuses on teachers satisfaction by considering their personal preferences.	4.44	0.58	O
3. provides teachers with assistance to overcome problems that stop them from carrying out their tasks.	4.50	0.56	HO
4. shows concern with their teachers' mental health and well-being.	4.49	0.58	O
5. behaves in a manner that is thoughtful of teachers' needs.	4.48	0.59	O
Overall	4.54	0.55	HO

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed

The table shows that the teacher respondents perceived Goal Setting and Expectancy as to Supportive as Highly Observed. Among the indicators, maintaining friendly working relationship with teachers and providing teachers with assistance has the highest mean. One of the main roles of principal is to provide leadership and coordination within the school. In Tiaong, principals can empower teachers to support instructional leadership through mentoring and giving technical assistance, by leading learning workshops and maintaining friendly working relationship with teachers. In Tiaong, technical assistance was given to teachers quarterly especially after classroom observation, where in teachers were having post-conference with the Master teacher observer and principal.

Table 9. Perceived Decision Making as to Autocratic

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. decides what goals are to be achieved by the teachers.	4.20	0.79	O
2. directs and controls all school activities.	4.15	0.85	O
3. requires no additional input from his/her team in making decisions.	4.07	0.91	O
4. believes they have enough information in making decision.	4.14	0.81	O
5. dictates policies and procedures to be done in school.	4.10	0.83	O
Overall	4.13	0.77	O

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed

The table shows that the teacher respondents perceived Decision Making as to Autocratic as Observed. Autocratic leadership was still observed because Department of Education has organizational structure, for it clearly defines the roles, functions, scopes of authority and systems management to ensure that people are working together to accomplish everything at the right time and to

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achieve the common goal. This only means that personnel working in the department, follows command based from the leader of the organizational structure in Education.

Table 10. Perceived Decision Making as to Consultative

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. engages subordinates in the decision making.	4.43	0.54	O
2. considers suggestions and information given by teachers before making decisions.	4.41	0.59	O
3. encourages subordinates to present opinions.	4.41	0.54	O
4. identifies teachers' strengths and weaknesses in delivering instruction.	4.41	0.56	O
5. conducts an open forum where teachers can give their idea.	4.44	0.55	O
Overall	4.42	0.50	O

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed
2.0

The table shows that the teacher respondents perceived Decision Making as to Consultative as Observed. Consultation in schools involves seeking feedback through a formal conversation about an issue or proposal. Feedback incorporates the different opinions that people may hold in regard to matter under discussion. In Tiaong, since principal is the higher authority in school, any decision must be consulted to them. Principals conduct faculty meetings regularly to engage subordinates in the decision making by considering their suggestions as well as their strength and weaknesses.

Table 11. Perceived Decision Making as to Collaborative

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. welcomes and appreciates teachers thoughts and ideas.	4.45	0.57	O
2. ensures teachers equal participation in making decision.	4.44	0.60	O
3. discusses school's situations through meetings.	4.50	0.53	HO
4. structures work to avoid overload.	4.41	0.58	O
5. accepts teachers' ideas and opinions.	4.45	0.61	O
Overall	4.45	0.52	O

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Observed, 4.49-3.5 Observed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Observed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Observed, 1.49-1.0 Not Observed

The table shows that Contingency leadership practices as to decision making as to collaborative is observed. However, among the indicators, school situations are discussed through meetings is highly observed. This is because in Tiaong District, regular meetings of principals led by the supervisor were conducted weekly in the district office.

Most of the indicators were observe because regular meetings in schools were also done by the principal in order to discuss school situations and ensure participation of teachers in making decisions.

Table 12. Level of Work Commitment as to Participation

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. attend seminars and trainings for professional growth and development.	4.42	0.58	C
2. involve their own ideas and opinions in curriculum development.	4.44	0.55	C
3. extend their involvement in the overall decision making process in school.	4.39	0.57	C
4. participate in an open forum which everyone can give their ideas.	4.46	0.58	C
5. share their expertise with co-teachers.	4.48	0.60	C
Overall	4.44	0.50	C

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Committed, 4.49-3.5 Committed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Committed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Committed, 1.49-1.0 Not Committed

The table shows that teachers are committed in the level of commitment as to participation.

The district of Tiaong I conducts LAC sessions, school and district INSET. This is in line with DO no.35, s. known as the Policy on the Learning Action Cell(LAC), this policy fully supports continuing professional development of its teaching personnel. In line with this, generally, teachers qualities are highly observed by participating in the above mentioned activities. These trainings allows teachers to follow instructions, at the same time they can give their opinions and ideas through these seminars and trainings.

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Table 13. Level of Work Commitment as to Task-Orientation

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. focus on the completion of a particular task in school.	4.50	0.55	HC
2. formulate plans to achieve goals set by the school head.	4.50	0.54	HC
3. prioritize assigned task in school activities.	4.51	0.53	HC
4. improve teaching performance using different pedagogies.	4.51	0.56	HC
5. show concern with their teaching effectiveness.	4.53	0.52	HC
Overall	4.51	0.47	HC

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Committed, 4.49-3.5 Committed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Committed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Committed, 1.49-1.0 Not Committed

The table shows that teachers level of Work Commitment as to Task Orientation is Highly Committed. The main task of teachers is to provide quality education by being effective in the teaching learning process. In order to attain quality of learning, teachers must plan their lessons effectively and efficiently. In line with the implementation of Republic Act (RA) No. 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, the Department of Education (DepEd) issues the enclosed Policy Guidelines on Daily Lesson Preparation for the K to 12 Basic Education Program.

Table 14. Level of Work Commitment as to Motivation

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. participate in school activities with devotion and loyalty towards task.	4.56	0.55	HC
2. put a lot of effort in teaching.	4.55	0.52	HC
3. appreciate attending seminar/trainings and conducts research studies.	4.43	0.60	C
4. create own methods of completing tasks.	4.45	0.56	C
5. rejoice in recognition for good work or excellent performance.	4.52	0.56	HC
Overall	4.50	0.48	HC

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Committed, 4.49-3.5 Committed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Committed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Committed, 1.49-1.0 Not Committed

The table shows that teachers are Highly Committed in terms of Level of Work commitment as to Motivation. According to section 4 of article II in the code of Ethics for Professional Teachers Every teacher shall possess and actualize a full commitment and devotion to duty. This is why teachers are Highly Committed and put a lot of effort in teaching.

As stated in Article IV section 3 of the Code of Ethics, Every teacher shall participate in the Continuing Professional Education (CPE) program of the Professional Regulation Commission, and shall pursue such other studies as will improve his efficiency, enhance the prestige of the profession, and strengthen his competence, virtues, and productivity in order to be nationally and internationally competitive.

Table 15. Level of Work Performance as to Teaching Effectiveness

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. motivate learners to perform and maintain high academic standards.	4.54	0.52	HP
2. conduct self -evaluation to improve teaching strategies.	4.52	0.55	HP
3. attain highly proficient to outstanding rating in RPMS(Result Based Performance Management System).	4.35	0.58	P
4. improve learners' performance manifested by MPS.	4.46	0.56	P
5. use variety of teaching strategies.	4.49	0.53	P
Overall	4.47	0.47	P

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Performed, 4.49-3.5 Performed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Performed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Performed, 1.49-1.0 Not Performed

The table shows that teachers are performing in terms of Level of Work Performance as to Teaching Effectiveness. However, among indicators, motivating to perform learners and maintain high academic standards and conducting self-evaluation to improve teaching strategies are Highly Performed.

This is evident in the Annual RPMS portfolio of teachers, this is a tool for assessment instruments used to ensure quality teacher performance at different career stages. The main purpose of this portfolio is for teacher evaluation. This type of document manages, monitors, and measures the performance of school teachers. Through classroom observations, trainings and seminars as well as their teaching effectiveness as shown in the MPS result of pupils assessment.

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Table 16. Level of Work Performance as to Learning Delivery

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. manage ethics and discipline in class.	4.54	0.53	HP
2. use appropriate techniques in teaching.	4.50	0.53	HP
3. align activities according to different learning styles of pupils.	4.50	0.55	HP
4. design effective strategies for learners.	4.53	0.53	HP
5. develop variety of instructional materials suited to learners needs.	4.50	0.55	HP
Overall	4.51	0.49	HP

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Performed, 4.49-3.5 Performed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Performed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Performed, 1.49-1.0 Not Performed

The table shows that teachers are Highly Performing in terms of Level of Work Performance as to Learning Delivery. This is because the main role of teachers is to deliver quality Education. Under DepED Memorandum No. 291 dated June 13, 2008 6 hours is devoted to the actual teaching of teachers while the remaining 2 hours spent for teaching- related activities except lunch breaks and recess periods. Teachers in Tiaong used the remaining 2 hours for Lesson Planning and Remediation. As stated in Article IV, section 2, Every teacher shall uphold the highest possible standards of quality education, shall make the best preparations for the career of teaching, and shall be at his best at all times and in the practice of his profession.

Table 17. Level of Work Performance as to Managing Time

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. monitor progress and time spent on the tasks and classroom activities.	4.52	0.54	HP
2. observe punctuality.	4.51	0.54	HP
3. complete school task and activities ahead of time.	4.46	0.59	P
4. manage time and other duties assigned to him/her.	4.48	0.55	P
5. record daily school activities.	4.45	0.58	P
Overall	4.48	0.49	P

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Performed, 4.49-3.5 Performed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Performed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Performed, 1.49-1.0 Not Performed

The table shows that teachers are performing in terms of Level of Work Performance as to Managing Time. However, among indicators, Monitoring progress and time spent on the tasks and classroom activities as well as teachers punctuality has the highest mean. In Tiaong district, teachers are required to update daily log records and DTR for the principals to monitor teachers punctuality.

Table 18. Level of Work Performance as to Performing Duties

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. use goal setting to accomplish task on time.	4.45	0.57	P
2. participate in extra-curricular activities.	4.45	0.58	P
3. accomplish quality outputs and reports.	4.48	0.56	P
4. organize school activities.	4.47	0.59	P
5. take part in faculty meetings and trainings.	4.52	0.54	HP
Overall	4.47	0.50	P

Legend: 5.0-4.5 Highly Performed, 4.49-3.5 Performed, 3.49-2.5 Moderately Performed, 2.49- 1.5 Somewhat Performed, 1.49-1.0 Not Performed

The table shows that teachers are performing in terms of Level of Work Performance as to Performing duties. However, taking part in faculty meetings and trainings has the highest mean. Communication, bonding time, actual working with the personnel motivated teachers them to work with willingness. It was also stated that teachers accept additional task as a challenge for them to improve more their skills. The main duty of teachers is to facilitate learning as stated in Article III, section 1 of Magna Carta for Teachers , A teacher is a facilitator of learning and of the development of the youth; he shall, therefore, render the best service by providing an environment conducive to such learning and growth.

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Table 19. Test of significant relationship of contingency leadership and work performance

Contingency Leadership Model	Work Performance				
	Teaching Effectiveness	Learning Delivery	Managing Time	Performing Duties	Overall Work Performance
Situational Condition					
Leadership Style	.516**	.468**	.490**	.442**	.509**
Qualities of Followers	.568**	.563**	.520**	.466**	.562**
Situational Features	.567**	.521**	.496**	.457**	.542**
Goal Setting and Expectancy					
Directive Clarifying	.593**	.536**	.509**	.473**	.560**
Achievement-Oriented	.545**	.524**	.504**	.463**	.540**
Participative	.605**	.567**	.574**	.533**	.605**
Supportive	.568**	.562**	.517**	.464**	.560**
Decision Making					
Autocratic	.459**	.438**	.396**	.427**	.457**
Consultative	.614**	.592**	.544**	.547**	.610**
Collaborative	.602**	.551**	.552**	.527**	.593**
Overall Contingency Leadership	.678**	.636**	.613**	.588**	.668**

The table shows that there is a significant relationship between contingency Leadership and Work Commitment. In the district of Tiaong, principals practiced Contingency Leadership which resulted to Highly Committed teachers.

Contingency leadership and teachers participation are correlated since teachers are the implementer of curriculum as stated by Alsubaie(2016). Teachers in Tiaong are participative in terms of seminars and activities for professional growth and development. Contingency Leadership also correlates with motivation. Changes in the educational system enable school leaders to seek out more successful organizational behaviors and use various leadership mentoring techniques. These leadership types influence the teacher's feeling of motivation and other emerging behaviors. The management or leadership styles of a principal may have a significant impact on a teacher's experience at the school and are frequently noted as a source of dissatisfaction. Educational leaders have a critical job in influencing teacher conduct and building a thriving academic environment, essential to teacher motivation and student academic progress Arceo (2022).

As explained by Charry(2012) Contingency theories of leadership focus on particular variables related to the environment that might determine which style of leadership is best suited for a particular work situation. Contingency theories put forth the idea that the success of a leader hinges on the specific situation at hand. Certain factors come into play that defines whether a particular leader or leadership style will be effective for the given situation. Those factors include the task, the personality of the leader and the composition of the group that is meant to be led.

Lim and Nizam (2014) in their study defined work commitment as an individual trait that reflects loyalty or obedience and a desire to become an organization member and willing to contribute energy to organizations and professionals.

Educators and policymakers alike seek a frame for effective leadership that can produce sustainable school improvement and continuous teacher commitment (Lambertz, 2002) as cited by Ling (2012).

Table 20. Test of significant relationship of contingency leadership and work performance

Contingency Leadership Model	Work Performance				
	Teaching Effectiveness	Learning Delivery	Managing Time	Performing Duties	Overall Work Performance
Situational Condition					
Leadership Style	.516**	.468**	.490**	.442**	.509**
Qualities of Followers	.568**	.563**	.520**	.466**	.562**
Situational Features	.567**	.521**	.496**	.457**	.542**
Goal Setting and Expectancy					
Directive Clarifying	.593**	.536**	.509**	.473**	.560**
Achievement-Oriented	.545**	.524**	.504**	.463**	.540**
Participative	.605**	.567**	.574**	.533**	.605**
Supportive	.568**	.562**	.517**	.464**	.560**
Decision Making					
Autocratic	.459**	.438**	.396**	.427**	.457**
Consultative	.614**	.592**	.544**	.547**	.610**
Collaborative	.602**	.551**	.552**	.527**	.593**
Overall Contingency Leadership	.678**	.636**	.613**	.588**	.668**

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The table shows that there is a significant relationship between contingency Leadership and Work Performance. Most principals in Tiaong district practiced Contingency leadership which improves Work Performance of Teachers.

Teaching effectiveness of teachers was in the Annual RPMS portfolio of teachers, this is a tool for assessment instruments used to ensure quality teacher performance at different career stages. The main purpose of this portfolio is for teacher evaluation. This type of document manages, monitors, and measures the performance of school teachers. Through classroom observations, trainings and seminars as well as their teaching effectiveness as shown in the MPS result of pupils assessment. Most of the teachers in Tiaong got Very Satisfactory Rating. This type of document manages, monitors, and measures the performance of school teachers.

Contingency Leadership and Learning delivery also correlates, this is because the main role of teachers is to deliver quality Education. Under DepED Memorandum No. 291 dated June 13, 2008 6 hours is devoted to the actual teaching of teachers while the remaining 2 hours spent for teaching- related activities except lunch breaks and recess periods. Teachers in Tiaong used the remaining 2 hours for Lesson Planning and Remediation.

.Education experts all over the country work tirelessly to identify the salient points or domains needed in line with the vision of transforming the Filipino Teacher into a globally competitive one. Thus, National Competency-Based Teachers Standards (NCBTS) was born and Teacher Work Performance Appraisal was based on it as stated by Usop (2013).

Contingency Leadership also correlates with time management. In Tiaong district, teachers are required to update daily log records and DTR for the principals to monitor teachers punctuality.

Republic Act No. 4670, otherwise known as the “Magna Carta for Public School Teachers,” provides that teaching hours for teachers shall not be more than six hours. The Department of Education (DepEd) issued Memorandum 291 s. 2008 allowing teachers to allot six hours for actual classroom teaching per day while the remaining two hours to be spent in teaching-related activities.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the study, the following conclusion was formulated:

The findings gathered in the study led to the formulation of the following conclusion, there is significant relationship between contingency leadership model and work commitment and performance of classroom executives, thus null hypothesis is not sustained.

5. RECOMMENDATION

The result revealed that there is a significant relationship between contingency leadership model and work commitment and performance of classroom executives. The following recommendations are set forth:

1. The study recommends that the school heads and principal in every school of Tiaong district may practice Contingency leadership in their school to improve the work commitment and performance of teachers.
2. The supervisor may consider planning, organizing, conducting seminars, training or workshop for continuous professional development of teachers in Tiaong.
3. It is recommended that regular assessment of teachers performance may be done annually.
4. School administrators may develop program or series of activities to enhance teachers commitment and motivate and encourage high performance in teaching.
5. Similar studies may be conducted to look into the different sets of variables in other places or districts to verify the results of this study.

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